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ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES FOR MONITORING THE PROGRESS OF INSTALLATION WORKS

Abstract.

Objective. To determine the most effective artificial intelligence technology for monitoring the progress of installation works.

Methodology. To solve the task we used a comprehensive approach with the application of special research methods, including analysis, explanation, generalization, comparison.

Results. The conducted research allowed to reveal the dependence on the conditions of objects, where installation works are carried out, and the effectiveness of using one or another technology of artificial intelligence.

Practical significance. The results of the study provide more detailed information for practitioners on the choice of more effective artificial intelligence technology depending on the conditions of the construction site.

Keywords: progress monitoring, construction, engineering, artificial intelligence models.

Traditional methods of construction progress monitoring process are too time and resource consuming, which leads to errors in progress reporting and project delays [1, p.1].

The productivity of the construction industry is quite low. By collecting real-time data directly from the construction site, it is possible to identify major bottlenecks and help decision makers to increase productivity at construction sites [2, p.1].

Effective monitoring of the progress of building construction and infrastructure projects involves the use of BIM technology - Building Information Modeling, which includes the creation and management of digital representations of the physical and functional characteristics of buildings or other physical assets and facilities, supported by various tools, processes, tech-

nologies and contracts. A digital twin of the planned facility is created, then a UAV or any other robotic platform with a high-resolution photo-video camera is used to capture the construction site around the clock. All the footage is wirelessly transmitted in real time to be processed and analyzed by an artificial intelligence (AI) model. Typically, CNNs - pre-trained convolutional neural network models - are used for this purpose, which are effective for image recognition and processing due to their ability to recognize patterns in images. AI algorithms use the processed information to create a BIM model of the actual built object. Then, using the same AI algorithm, the models of the actually built object and the planned object are combined, which allows you to see the progress of construction in real time, Figure 1 [3, p. 14-15].

Figure 1. Real-time construction progress monitoring process.

The method described above is effective at different stages of construction. It is based on the use of UAVs and machine learning methods, such as for monitoring land development projects. Where a UAV flying or hovering over an object takes a photo-video survey, and a machine learning model identifies the desired objects and changes in the photo-video and automatically compares it with the design drawings, which allows you to evaluate the progress of the project.

Using UAVs for data collection is more feasible than other robotic platforms because when flying over a site, UAVs have a wider view and can collect data anywhere and anytime. Interaction with a 3D model of the object under construction for the detection of building elements with an accuracy of 82-84% [4, p. 1].

A more advanced approach to monitoring construction progress involves the use of computer vision with deep learning. The Mask Recurrent Convolutional Neural Network deep learning model is able to automatically perform construction progress monitoring using computer vision, a cloud-based platform that allows it to process and store data remotely from construction sites.

This method involves an automated data collection process using frame-by-frame cameras to capture a complete set of images, significantly reducing human intervention and associated errors. By utilizing multiple cameras positioned to capture images in different lighting conditions and angles, full coverage and accurate feature extraction is ensured, Figure 2 [5, p. 7-9].

Figure 2. Recognizing changes in indoor condition using Mask R-CNN.

The application of computer vision-based methods for object recognition and real-time location system (RTLS) for object localization is the next more advanced version of the above methods. This method combines the data obtained by the deep learning model and the ultra-wideband (UWB) system and reports the ID of each element, location, visual data and capture time, which provides information for real-time progress assessment. This method is effective in the indoor environment with a large number of HVAC elements,

which, for example, can create significant difficulties for UAV operation due to signal interference and occlusion. The working principle of the automatic object recognition model involves classifying the tracked components in images in real time, while allowing the UWB system to provide a unique ID and location of the corresponding components in real time, which makes this method the most effective for the HVAC field, Figure 3 [6, p. 6-8].

Figure 3. Overview of the process of integrating the results of object recognition and localization.

Discussion and conclusion:

Automated monitoring of the progress of installation works using a digital twin is an effective approach in closed-loop project management. With BIM technology, engineers can have an accurate and up-to-date view of the project progress, which can then be used to identify potential problems and make informed decisions.

Image data analytics using machine learning methods such as SVM can process large amounts of photo and video data obtained from UAVs. Therefore, the introduction of machine learning methods in UAV data analytics can significantly improve the monitoring of the progress of construction projects. The effectiveness of machine learning largely depends on the quality of the data used.

While switching to digital platforms for monitoring the progress of installation works provides long-term cost and time savings, it requires personnel training and investment.

The RTLS model provides accurate location information and a unique identifier for each element of air ducts and pipes, which makes it ideal for the HVAC industry.

All methods show their effectiveness compared to traditional methods.

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